

Comparison of the effectiveness of some plant extracts as botanical insecticides in soybean farming in Tidal Swampland

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ABSTRACT

*Environmental degradation has reduced the quality of people's life, especially in developing countries. Therefore, since the 1970s the world community began to pay greater attention to environmental issues, in the context of sustainable development. This can be seen with the Stockholm Conference, Agenda 21 at the Rio Earth Summit, and the Johannesburg Declaration. However, although the commitment and great attention was given at the international level, environmental conditions are still deteriorating. One of the causes is the synthetic pesticides application for controlling pests and plant diseases. The long experience has proven that synthetic pesticides application in plant protection programs has resulted in various disorders such as environmental damage, pest resurgence and resistance, natural enemies' mortality and human health problems. Therefore, it is very important to get a substitute for synthetic insecticides which is the one of the environmental pollutant sources. The alternatives that need to be developed are utilizing of toxic compounds found in plants known as botanical insecticides. Swampland has great potential of plant species that contain botanic insecticides. This study aims to identify the toxicity of plant extracts of plant-based insecticides for controlling soybean crops pests in tidal swamp land. The laboratory test for the toxicity effects of kirinyu leaf extract (*Chromolaena odorata*), kepayang (*Pangium edule*), bintaro (*Carberamanghas*) and extract of Java chili fruit (*Piper retrofractum*) and forest betel (*Piper aduncum*) in 3rd instar *Spodopteralitura* larvae, concluded that those plant extracts were able to kill 3rd instar *Spodopteralitura* larvae with 84%, 93%, 92%, 46% and 92% respectively after 72 hours of observation. Furthermore, the efficacy test of those five plant extracts in soybean cultivation in the tidal swampland of Central Kalimantan showed that Java chili was shown as the lowest leaf damage level (8.0%) followed by kepayang (9.2%). Then, kepayang treatment also has the highest ability in suppressing pods damage both caused by pod borer and pod sucker, with 60.69% and 71.99% respectively. Plots with kirinyu extract treatment has the highest predatory arthropod abundance of 423 (48.85%).*

Keywords: Sustainability, soybean, botanic insecticide, tidal swampland

INTRODUCTION

Environmental degradation has reduced the quality of people life, especially in developing countries. Therefore, the world community since the 1970s began to pay greater attention to the environmental issues, in the context of sustainable development. This can be seen with the Stockholm Conference (1972), Agenda 21 at the Rio Earth Summit (1992), and the Johannesburg Declaration (2002). However, although the commitment and great attention given at the international level, environmental conditions are still declining. One of the causes is the use of synthetic pesticides for the eradication of pests and plant diseases.

In the past, synthetic pesticides have played a major role in crop protection programs and have greatly benefited humans. The long practice has proven that the use of synthetic pesticides in crop protection programs has resulted in various disorders such as environmental damage, pest resurgence and resistance, useful insect deaths and human health problems (Manuwoto, 1999; Arinafril and Muller, 1999; Thamrin et al., 1999; Thamrin et al. 2013). Therefore, it is very important to get a substitute for synthetic insecticides which is one of the sources of this environmental pollutant.

In order to achieve soybean self-sufficiency, it is necessary to increase soybean production in the sustainable and safely manner. However, soybean farming system development is constrained by high risk of pest attacks from planting until harvesting and storage. The efforts have been made to control the t soybeans insect and pest, such as the use of pesticides. Synthetic pesticides are still considered as the most effective way to control insect and pest. However, unwise use of synthetic pesticides can lead to environmental pollution, mortality of non-target insect, simplification of natural food chains and biodiversity (Norris et al. 2003 in Baliadi et al. 2012). In addition, synthetic insecticides not only negatively affect insect life but also flora and fauna systems and human health (Manuwoto, 1999). Given this situation for improving sustainability of soybean farming system, there is an increased interest in using of alternative substances of synthetic insecticide with less risk to the environment and human health while increasing soybean production.

An alternative that needs to be developed is to utilize toxic compounds found in plants known as botanic insecticides. Botanic insecticides are generally defined as a pesticide whose active ingredients come from plants which are toxic to disturbing organisms and have a group of secondary metabolites containing various bioactive compounds. At least 2000 types of plants from various families have been reported to adversely affect plant disturbing organisms (Prakash and Rao, 1977; Grainge and Ahmed, 1987), among which there are at least 850 active plant species that are toxic to insects (Prakash and

Rao, 1977). Some plants consist of several components that are toxic to insects. When extracted and applied to insect pests, this component is called botanic pesticide. Most botanic pesticides are contact, respiratory or stomach poison, so the nature is not very selective and the target is a broad insect. Although useful insects are exposed to botanic pesticides, due to their low toxicity the negative effects on useful insects can be minimized through selective applications. Furthermore, botanic pesticides are generally very easily biodegradable, so they become inactive within a few hours or days. So that the negative impact on useful organisms is very small and generally relatively safe for the environment.

Swampland has great potential in terms of plant species that contain natural insecticides. Asikin and Thamrin (2006) and Thamrin et al. (2007) reported that there are 24 plants that are often found in swampland and have the potential as botanic insecticides, namely *binderang* (*Scleriaoblata*), swamp daffodils (*Crynumasiaticum*), *simpur* (*Dillenasuffruticosa*), *pulantan wood* (*Alstoniasp*), *buta-but*a (*Excoecariaagalocha*), *mahang wood* (*Macarangajavanica*), *kakambat* (*Justiciasp*), *jingah* (*Glutharengas*), *jengkol* (*Phitecellobiumlobatum*), *sungkai* (*Peronemacanescen*), *halaban wood* (*Vitexpubescens*), *usar* (*Dianellasp*), *jeruju* (*Acanthus illicifollius*), *putat* (*Bringtoniasp*), *lenggundi* (*Vitextrifolia*), *karetan* (*Ficuselastika*), *binjai* (*Mangifera caesia*), *mengkudu* (*Morindacitrifolia*), *sapang* (*Abrospreca torius*), *banyam* (*Ficusbenyamina*), *mamali* (*Lersia sp.*), *Kumandrah* (*Croton tiglium*) and *mangrove* (*Rhizophorasp*).

The results of several plant bioassays research at the Balittra Laboratory showed that plant-based insecticides from *chromolainodorata* were able to kill instar 2 armyworm larvae with 84% mortality, while *kepayang* plants (*Pangiumedule*) and *bintaro* (*Carberamanghas*) were able to kill instar 2 larvae and instar 3 were 88%, 86%, 86% and 82%, respectively (Thamrin et al., 2015). While the results of Indriati's research (2015) showed *H. antonii* imago, mortality due to treatment of *java chili* fruit extract 0.05% -0.3% has occurred since 24 hours after treatment (JSP). *Java chili* extract which is exposed in the sun for up to 5 days is still effective in killing *H. antonii* imago (80% mortality) but is not effective in inhibiting egg laying by *H. antonii* females. Inhibition of egg laying on *H. antonii* imago was only observed in the treatment of *Java chili* extract 0.98% (2 x LC95) exposed under the sun for 0 and 1 day, with the oviposition inhibition index 22.7% and 23.8% respectively.

The research aims to identify the toxicity of plant insecticide extracts on laboratory test and identify the efficacy of plant insecticide extracts that are effective in controlling soybean leaves and pods in tidal land.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Five types of plants used in this study were kirinyu (*Chromolaenaodorata*), kepayang (*Pangiumedule*), bintaro (*Cerberaodollam*), Java chilli (*Piper retrofractumVahl*) and forest betel (*Piper aduncum*) (Figure 1). Plant extract toxicity tests were carried out in the pest laboratory of the Department of Protection of Bogor University and Wetland Research Institute in May - June 2017. Then, efficacy trials of plant extracts were carried out in the dry season of August - November 2017 in tidal swamp land, Sidomulyo Village, Tamban Catur Sub-district, Kapuas Regency (Central Kalimantan).

Figure 1. bintaro (*Cerberaodollam*), Kepayang (*Pangiumedule*), kirinyu (*Chromolaenaodorata*), cabaijawa (*Piper retrofractum*) and sirihhutan (*P. aduncum*) (Left – Right)

Extraction of plant parts is done by maceration method. Extraction process was started by collecting of plants and cleaning from dirt and damaged parts. Each plant material was cut into small pieces and dried for 1-2 weeks. Then, each ingredient was mashed using a blender to become a powder and sieved using a wire sieve with a wire braid measuring 0.5 mm. 500 g of the each plant powder was soaked separately with a solvent at a ratio of 1:10 (w/v), then stirred and left for 24 hours in a dark room. The filtrates which are filtered using a glass funnel which is coated with filter paper were collected in evaporating flasks and evaporated using a rotary evaporator at a temperature of 50°C and a pressure of 240 mbar until crude extract was obtained. Each extract obtained

was stored in the refrigerator ($\pm 4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) until it is used for testing. The extraction process can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Steps of extraction process

The insect used in this study was a third instar of *Spodopteralitura* (Lepidoptera: *Noctuidae*), which was maintained and propagated in the laboratory. Preliminary tests were carried out for each plant extract using leaf dipping method for evaluating effect of stomach poison on *Spodopteralitura* larvae.

Field research on tidal swamp land was carried out on Randomized Block Design (RBD) with eight treatments and four replications. The treatments consisted of plant extracts of bintaro, Java chili, kepayang, kirinyu and betel forest, while insecticides with active ingredients of chlorantraniliprol 50 gr/l was used as synthetic insecticides control and non-insecticide treatment were used as a control.

The first treatment application is based on leaf damage level, while the next applications were carried out every week until the end of the pod filling phase. The dosage of botanic insecticides is 2 g/liter of water, and 2 ml/liter of water for synthetic chemistry. The spray volume used is 500 liter/ha or 1.25 liter/plot. The treatment application is done in the afternoon when the sun has gone down.

Observation of leaf damage was done by calculating the number of damaged leaves in the clumps of plants in each research plot. Observation of leaf damage is carried out every week during plant growth. Calculation of leaf

damage due to destructive pest attack is using the Sastrosiswojo formula (1984) as follows:

$$I = \frac{\sum(n \times v)}{Z \times N} \times 100\%$$

I = Attacks intensity (%)

n = Number of damaged plants

V = Scale value of each attack category.

Z = The highest scale value

N = The number of plant samples observed

Scale value for each category of pest attack on soybean plant leaves:

Attack 0 = No attacks

Attack 1 = Leaf area eaten by insect 1-10%

Attack 2 = Leaf area eaten by insect > 10-25%

Attack 3 = Leaf area eaten insect > 25-50%

Attack 4 = Leaf area eaten by insect > 50-75%

Attack 5 = Leaf area eaten by insect > 75%

Damage to pods and seeds due to pod pests is calculated by:

$$\text{Percentage of pods damage} = \frac{\text{Number of pods damage} \times 100\%}{\text{Total number of pods}}$$

$$\text{Percentage of damage seeds} = \frac{\text{Number of seeds damage} \times 100\%}{\text{Total number of seeds}}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the toxicity test showed that Kirinyu leaf extract was able to kill insect test larvae with 84% mortality, while kepayang and bintaro plants were 93% and 92% respectively after 72 hours of observation (Table 1). Java chilli (*Piper retrofractum*) and forest betel (*Piper aduncum*) showed that the best potential was at a concentration of 4% with mortality 46% and 92% after 72 hours of observation (Table 1).

Table 1. Toxicity test results of plant extracts in *Spodopteralituralarvae* at laboratory

Plant extract (4%)	% mortality		
	24 hours	48 hours	72 hours
<i>Carberamanghas</i>	11	68	92
<i>Pangiumedule</i>	25	80	93
<i>Chromolainadorata</i>	73	98	84
<i>Piper aduncum</i>	40	46	46
<i>Piper retrofractum</i>	58	94	98

The results of observations on the damage of soybean leaves mostly caused by army worm (*Spodopteralitura*) and leaf beetles (*Alticabrevicosta*) with damage levels ranging from 8.0-27, 7%.The treatment with the lowest leaf damage level was shown by *Piper retrofractum*(8.0%) on observations of 7 week after planting (wap) and *Pangiumedule*(9.2%) at 9 wapoobservation, while the kirinyu treatment showed consistent reduction effectiveness on observations 5, 6, 7 and 8 wap (18.6%; 12.1%; 8.3%; 8.0%)(Table 2). So the three treatments can be considered for further research, especially their effectiveness on soybean leaf pests (Figure 3).

Tabel 2. The difference test in the middle value of soybean leaf damage in tidal swampland

Treatments	Palnt age				
	5 wap	6 wap	7 wap	8 wap	9 wap
<i>Pangiumedule</i>	0,175 a	0,122 a	0,081 cd	0,081 c	0,092 c
<i>Chromolaenaodorata</i>	0,186 a	0,121 a	0,083 cd	0,080 c	0,108 bc
<i>Cerberaodollam</i>	0,184 a	0,115 a	0,087 cd	0,081 c	0,110 bc
<i>Piperaduncum</i>	0,168 a	0,162 a	0,136 ab	0,137 ab	0,125 b
<i>Piper retrofractum</i>	0,169 a	0,183 a	0,080 d	0,081 c	0,101 bc
Chemical	0,113 b	0,125 a	0,112 bc	0,091 bc	0,094 bc
Control	0,167 a	0,182 a	0,152 a	0,149 a	0,165 a

Wap = week after planting

The numbers on the same track followed by the same lowercase letters are different not significantly according to the DNMRT at the level of 5%.

Figure 3. Results of the efficacy test of plant extracts on soybean leaf pests on tidal swamp land

The average ability of each treatment to suppress leaf damage in a row was kepayang (19.37%), kirinyu (16.32%), bintaro (14.32%), chillijawa (11.51%) and betel forest (8.14%) (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Percentage of leaf damage reduction by treatment

Observations on pod damage were carried out on pods that were damaged due to soybeans pod suckers (*Nezaraviridula*, *Riptortuslinearis*) and pod borer (*Etiellazinknella*). Both of these pests are important pests of the generative

stage of soybean plants. Observations on pod damage caused by pod suckers ranged from 0.0 to 32.45%. The difference in treatment was seen in the 8 wap, but in the observation of 9 mst and 12 mst there was no difference in treatment. There was a decrease in pod damage at 9 mst observation, but it increased again at 12 mst (Table 3). While the results of observations of pod damage caused by pod borers did not show any differences in treatment in all observations (Table 4). In general, *Pangiumedule* has the highest ability to reduce damage to pods both caused by borer and sucker, with consecutive emphasis of 60.69% and 71.99% (Figure 5).

Table 3. The difference test in the middle value of soybean pod sucker in tidal swampland

Treatments	Plant age		
	8 wap	9 wap	12 wap
<i>Pangiumedule</i>	2,56 ab	0,91 a	26,74 a
<i>Chromolaenaodorata</i>	1,55 ab	0,29 a	25,65 a
<i>Cerberaodollam</i>	0,00 b	1,45 a	29,40 a
<i>Piperaduncum</i>	14,71ab	7,19 a	32,45 a
<i>Piper retrofractum</i>	2,27 ab	0,42 a	27,57 a
Chemical	9,12 ab	4,30 a	17,15 a
Control	16,23 ab	6,06 a	30,31 a

Wap = week after planting

The numbers on the same track followed by the same lowercase letters are different not significantly according to the DNMRT at the level of 5%.

Table 4. The difference test in the middle value of soybean pod borer in tidal swampland

Treatments	Plant age		
	8 wap	9 mst	12 mst
<i>Pangiumedule</i>	8,18 a	14,42 a	2,55 a
<i>Chromolaenaodorata</i>	2,79 a	15,06 a	5,63 a
<i>Cerberaodollam</i>	5,73 a	16,50 a	0,99 a
<i>Piperaduncum</i>	2,26 a	21,85 a	6,98 a
<i>Piper retrofractum</i>	3,87 a	9,98 a	0,00 a
Chemical	2,65 a	4,18 a	0,09 a
Control	9,91 a	19,22 a	5,12 a

Wap = week after planting

The numbers on the same track followed by the same lowercase letters are different not significantly according to the DNMRT at the level of 5%.

Figure 5. Percentage of pod damage in each treatment

The plant that use as botanic insecticides such as *Pangium edule* contain of flavonoids and saponin that are very effective in killing insects that are used as the main ingredient of insecticides. Flavonoids can affect the insect's respiratory system while saponins affect the digestive system (Carlos 2001). Saponins will damage the structure and permeability of insect cell membranes, so that the components in the cell exit and cause the death of insects (Shargel and Yu 1988). *Pangium edule* is also known to contain cyanide which is high enough to reach 350 g/tree. Cyanide is a toxic material produced by the hydrolysis process of cyanogen glycosides by enzymes found in the plant itself. One of the active compounds found in the *Pangium edule* is pyrethrin. Pyrethrin act very quickly to interfere with the insect's nerve tissue so that it can instantly faint insects (Goodwin, 1956), but is safe for humans and animals (Bailey, 1959; Rostiana et al. 1994; Lellan, 1963). pyrethrin is a contact poison that works quickly affecting the insect's nervous system, causing symptoms of paralysis and death (Worthing, 1987).

Observations on insect species and populations show the diversity of insect species both in pests and natural enemies. Recorded insects from the order Coleoptera, Lepidoptera, Hemiptera, Homoptera, Hymenoptera, Orthoptera, Odonata, and even found from the Arachnida (spiders). Natural enemies in the form of parasitoids from the Hymenoptera group are found in fairly high numbers (89%), other types of natural enemies are also found from the coleopteran (beetle) and arachnida (spider) groups. The treatment of chlorantraniliprol chemical pesticide control has a catch population value of pest insects and the lowest natural enemy (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Number of natural enemies found in field experiment

CONCLUSIONS

This study find out that *kepayang* (*Pangiumedule*) has highest ability to kill *Spodopteralitura* larvae with 93 % mortality at laboratory test. In general, the field experiment investigated that *kepayang* has the highest ability to suppress leaf damage (19.37%), and also to reduce pods damage caused by pod borer and pod sucker, with consecutive emphasis of 60.69% and 71.99%. All treatments have higher number of natural enemies than chemical treatment.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to thank to the IAARD (Indonesian Agency for Agriculture Research and Development), through KP4S which was funded the research. Our appreciation goes also to the ISARI (Indonesian Swampland Agriculture Research Institute) for opportunity and support to the research.

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